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LIBRO DE RESÚMENES

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PRESENTACIÓN

[AEQUA-Asociación Española para el Estudio del Cuaternario](#) es una entidad científica de carácter multidisciplinar, fundada en el año 1972, que aglutina a las/os investigadoras/es que trabajan sobre el periodo Cuaternario (últimos 2,6 millones de años). Es miembro de INQUA-International Union for Quaternary Research desde 1980. AEQUA convoca reuniones científicas cada dos años: una Reunión Nacional y una Reunión Ibérica que van alternándose. La XIV Reunión Nacional se celebró en el Palacio de la Madraza de Granada en julio de 2015 y la IX Reunión de Cuaternario Ibérico tuvo lugar en la Universidad de Algarve (Faro, Portugal) en octubre de 2017. Durante la última asamblea general de AEQUA celebrada en Granada se aprobó la organización en Bilbao de la XV Reunión Nacional de Cuaternario, cuyo tema general es “Cambios ambientales y Huella humana”.

El País Vasco presenta una larga tradición cuaternarista, dentro de cuyos principales hitos es posible destacar la publicación en el año 1917 de los primeros trabajos científicos sobre prehistoria vasca realizados por José Miguel de Barandiaran, Telesforo de Aranzadi y Enrique Eguren, la fundación en 1947 de la [Sociedad de Ciencias Aranzadi](#) para la investigación del

medio natural y el patrimonio cultural, la celebración en 1990 de la primera reunión científica en Vitoria-Gasteiz bajo el título de *International Conference on the Environment and the Human Society in the Western Pyrenees and the Basque Mountains during the Upper Pleistocene and the Holocene* y, por último, el inicio en 2009 de los estudios universitarios de postgrado en Cuaternario: Cambios Ambientales y Huella Humana en la Universidad del País Vasco UPV/EHU ([Máster](#) y [Doctorado](#)).

Esta Reunión Nacional está organizada por la [Unidad de Formación e Investigación en Cuaternario](#) de la UPV/EHU, que desarrolla actividades docentes e investigadoras ligadas al estudio multidisciplinar de secuencias sedimentarias recientes. El objetivo de este congreso es la presentación de resultados científicos novedosos por parte de investigadoras/es y estudiantes de postgrado que muestren el avance en los estudios cuaternaristas desde el punto de vista geológico, prehistórico y antropológico, fomentando la discusión constructiva entre todas/os las/os participantes.

DECODING CONTOURITE SUCCESSIONS IN TERMS OF BOTTOM CURRENT SPEEDS IN THE SW MEDITERRANEAN OVER THE LAST 24 Ka

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Resumen (Decodificación de la sucesión de facies de contornitas en términos de la velocidad de las corrientes de fondo en el Mediterráneo occidental durante los últimos 24 ka): Se presenta un estudio sedimentológico y cronoestratigráfico de las contornitas del Mar de Alborán (Mediterráneo SO) en base al registro sedimentario de dos testigos de sedimento. En este estudio se incorporan marcadores físicos de corrientes de fondo ("sortable silt mean grain size" mean_{ss}) y marcadores químicos de cambios ambientales (Si/Si+Al y Zr/Al ratios) con el objeto de decodificar las sucesiones de contorníticas en términos de variabilidad de velocidad de las corrientes de fondo en relación con cambios paleoambientales. Estos resultados son validados con la inclusión del registro del mean_{ss} de un testigo localizado en el Mediterráneo Nor-Occidental. Este transecto proporciona una perspectiva regional de los cambios de velocidades de la corriente profunda del Mediterráneo Occidental durante los últimos 24 ka B.P.

Palabras clave: Contornitas, corrientes de fondo, Mar de Alborán

Key words: Contourites, bottom currents, Alboran Sea

INTRODUCTION

Sediments transported by bottom currents accumulate on sediment drifts and are known as contourites (Stow et al., 2002). As a consequence, contourites represent the best deposits for studying changes in the intensity of bottom currents and them for reconstructing palaeocirculation and to understand the ocean-climate link. Palaeocurrent reconstruction studies with high temporal resolution document the need for sensitive parameters from rapidly accumulating and continuously deposited fine sediments. Considerable advances have been made in sensitive parameters of palaeocurrent, utilizing chemical and physical proxies as tracers of bottom current velocity (McCave and Hall, 2000; Bianchi et al., 2001; Spooner et al., 2018; among others). The most important parameter is the direct physical proxy of bottom current circulation based on the grain size characteristics of marine sediments as an alternative to chemical tracers (e.g., Mg/Ca, Cd/Ca ratio in benthic foraminifera, benthic isotopes).

Most previous studies in the Alboran Sea have focussed on understanding the paleoproductivity /temperatures /redox-conditions in surface and deep-water masses using various chemical proxies (Cacho et al., 1999; Colmenero et al., 2004; Martrat et al., 2005; Moreno et al., 2004; Jimenez-Espejo et al., 2007; among others). While works on physical proxies (e.g., sortable silt mean grain size) of deep

waters are scarce over the last 20 ka (Rodríguez-Gámiz et al., 2011).

In the Alboran region the occurrence of extensive Plio-Quaternary contourite drifts has recently been well documented using geophysical methods (Ercilla et al., 2016; Juan et al., 2016). However, the sedimentological and geochemical characteristics of the contourite drifts have not yet been documented, in spite of the fact that they provide a record of palaeoceanographic-/climatic changes. In this context, the purpose of this study is primarily to elucidate the nature of the drift contourites. The secondary aim is to decode contourite facies successions in terms of bottom current speed variability and climate during the last 24 Ka.

LOCATION

The Alboran Sea is located in the westernmost basin of the Mediterranean Sea, limited by the Iberian Peninsula (Spanish margin) and North Africa (Moroccan margin). It is bounded by the Algero-Balear Basin in the east and the Strait of Gibraltar in the west. On the distal Alboran margins, the Plio-Quaternary sedimentation is influenced principally by bottom currents, being locally affected by turbidity and mass flows.

From an oceanographic point of view, the Alboran Sea is the exchange zone between the Mediterranean Sea and the Atlantic Ocean, through the Strait of Gibraltar. At the surface, Atlantic Water (AW) flows show two anticyclonic gyres. At a greater depth are: the Western Intermediate Water (WIW), the Levantine Intermediate Water (LIW), and the Western Mediterranean Deep Water (WMDW) (Ercilla et al., 2016).

Fig. 1: Map showing the location of sediment cores.

METHODS

Two sediment cores (C8 and M8) have been studied and they were recovered from Alboran contourite drifts swept by the WMDW. C8 is located at the Western Spanish base of slope, at 914 m water depth. M8 is situated at slope of SW western Alboran Basin at 753 m water depth. The cores have been analysed using stratigraphic, sedimentological, and geochemical tools.

Stratigraphy. For one of the cores, C8, there is a previously published age model (Ausin et al., 2015). Age model of M8 is constrained by five samples with AMS¹⁴C radiocarbon analyses and stable oxygen isotope ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$) measurements which are compared with the well-dated core C8 (fifteen AMS¹⁴C data) and ODP 977 (Martrat et al., 2004) $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ records in the Alboran Sea.

Sedimentology. Texture, carbonate content, ichnofacies, sedimentary structures and sand fraction composition have been analyzed. The grain size distribution of the terrigenous fraction was obtained using a Coulter LS 100 laser particle-size analyser (CLS 100). This analysis of carbonate-free sediment was achieved by treating the samples with hydrochloric acid (HCl) beforehand, to remove the carbonate. Likewise, to infer past palaeocurrent intensity, we employed the mean grain size of the terrigenous 10-63 μm fraction, known as sortable mean grain size (mean_{ss}). The speed changes were evaluated by applying the calibration of mean_{ss} and flow speed of near-bottom currents from McCave et al. (2017). A total of 493 samples were analysed.

Geochemistry. We used the Si/Si+Al ratio as a proxy of arid/humid conditions and Zr/Al as a proxy for eolian conditions according to previous studies (Moreno et al., 2004; Barth et al., 2017). The relative contents of these elements were measured on split sediment at 1 cm intervals using an Avaatech X-ray fluorescence (XFR).

RESULTS

Age model

The age model covers the last 24 ka, allowing the identification of two climatic periods: the last glacial (MIS 2) and the Holocene (MIS 1). MIS 2 defines the Heinrich Event 2 (HE 2; record available only in core C8), Heinrich Event 1 (HE 1) and the Younger Dryas (YD). The sedimentation rate shows the high values are in cores C8 (11-111 cm/ka) and M8 (14-190 cm/ka). According to these data and sampling, the studied cores have high temporal resolution (core C8 of ~ 80 years and core M8 of ~ 300 years).

Contourite facies

Three contourite facies (1 to 3) have been defined. Facies 1 is predominant and comprises silty-clay, representing the finest-grained sediments; Facies 2 involves bioturbated clayey-silt; Facies 3 consists of the coarsest sediments (sand). The mainly fine-grained contourites allow us to classify the Alboran contourite drifts as “muddy contourites”.

The vertical successions of the above facies enable us to identify two sedimentary sequences, A and B from older to younger (Fig. 2). Both sequences have a bigradational pattern with a progressive increase and then decrease of grain-size referred to as coarsening-up and fining-up. Sequence A (24 to 25.2 ka) is defined by the vertical successions of lithofacies 1-2-3-2-1. This sequence display the highest values of mean grain size (up 170 μm in core C8) and mean_{ss} (up to 41 μm). These maximum values are coincident with the maximum peaks of the Zr/Al and Si/Si+Al ratios (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Summary of the sedimentological and geochemical parameters characterizing sequences A and B. Core photos show vertical distribution of contourites.

Sequence B (24 to 0 ka) comprises the vertical succession of lithofacies 1-2-1, representing the finer-grained deposits, and is the dominant sequence for the Alboran contourite drifts. This sequence that repeat in the vertical, shows the maximum mean grain-size (up to 10.5 μm in core M8, and 50 μm in core C8) and mean_{ss} values (up to 21.6 μm in core M8 and 32 μm in core C8) are minor to the sequence A. These high grain-size values coincide with the maximum peaks of the Zr/Al and Si/Si+Al ratios (Fig. 2).

Sortable silt mean grain size (mean_{ss})

The temporal distribution of $mean_{ss}$ reveals differences between the two climate periods MIS 1 and MIS 2, with low ($18-15 \mu m$) and high ($18-32 \mu m$) values, respectively. At millennial time-scale, the distribution of $mean_{ss}$ shows a common overall pattern, with four synchronous periods over the last 24 ka identified for the first time in the Alboran region (labelled I to IV, from older to younger in Fig. 3). The ages of these periods are the followings. Period I: $\sim 23-17$ ka; Period II: $\sim 17-15$ ka; Period III: $\sim 15-10$ ka; and Period IV: $\sim 10-5$ ka.

Fig. 3: Distribution of $mean_{ss}$ of WMDW over the last 24 ka showing: i) four synchronous periods; ii) the quantification of the flow speed changes (cm/s); and iii) magnitude changes in $mean_{ss}$. (Core MD99-2343: Frigola et al., 2007); a-acceleration, b-deceleration; s-steady events of WMDW.

DISCUSSION

In the Alboran muddy contourites, Sequence A corresponds to the complete standard contourite sequence of Stow et al. (2002; divisions C1 to C5). This sequence suggests a winnowing effect during the period of enhanced bottom current activity evidenced by the maximum mean grain-size peak (Fig. 2). Sequence B corresponds to partial contourite sequences. Each sequence is linked to shifts in the strength of the bottom currents, from weak to strong and then back to weak (Fig. 3).

With respect to bottom current velocity, the two sequences include only low-energy environments (contourite drift), while high-energy environments are not recorded (e.g., channels), similarly to muddy contourite drifts from other regions (Stow et al., 2002). To date, the flow speed changes of the bottom

currents associated with these deposits have not yet been quantitatively well documented. Here, bottom current flow speeds are inferred through magnitude changes in $mean_{ss}$ within the sequence type B. This provides information on the WMDW palaeocurrent scenarios during the construction of the Alboran contourite drifts.

Paleohydrodynamic scenarios of the WMDW

The dynamics of the WMDW flow can be summarized as four synchronous periods, I to IV, over the last 24 ka (Fig. 3). Periods I to III comprise acceleration and deceleration events reflected by corresponding increased/decreased in $mean_{ss}$ (Fig. 3). Period IV is characterized by bottom current acceleration, stability, and deceleration ($\sim 10-3$ ka). To decode the contourite facies successions in terms of bottom current speeds, we have compared two binary plots (Fig. 4): magnitude changes in $mean_{ss}$ and changes in WMDW flow speed (in cm/s) versus four periods of bottom current acceleration. The bottom current speeds for each acceleration periods correspond to: ~ 2 to 6 cm/s for Ia; ~ 3 to 5 cm/s for IIa; ~ 4 to 9 cm/s for IIIa; and ~ 1 to 9 cm/s for IVa reaching this speed up to the stability period (Fig. 3). These palaeospeeds are in the same range as modern oceanographic data (Vargas-Yáñez et al., 2002; Com. Pers., Rosa Balbin).

The temporal distribution of the four Alboran acceleration periods of WMDW flow speed has been assessed using a similar record ($mean_{ss}$) from another contourite drift in the NW Mediterranean at 2391 m water depth (Fig. 4), and allow us to establish that WMDW flow have operated into two hydrodynamic scenarios during the last 24 ka. Scenario 1 associates to relatively lower bottom current speeds (< 5.5 cm/s) for the acceleration period IIa. Scenario 2 corresponds to higher bottom current speeds (up to ~ 12 cm/s) during the acceleration periods Ia, IIIa, and IVa (Figs. 3 and 4).

Fig. 4: Two binary plots, magnitude changes in $mean_{ss}$, (A) and changes in WMDW flow speed (B) versus four acceleration periods of WMDW. Med Mediterranean.

Millennial-scale climate imprint in contourites

The chronostratigraphic framework and sedimentological data from the cores show a clear relationship between millennial-scale climate variations and contourite grain-size. The lowest grain-size values are from the early Holocene, revealing the weakest WMDW flow. This flow reduction was synchronous with the deposition of an Organic Rich Layer in the Alboran Sea, defining a well-marked period in the Alboran Sea (Jiménez-Espejo et al., 2007).

Furthermore, $mean_{ss}$ and wind proxy (Si/Si+Al ratio) correlate in both sequences, with the highest values being recorded in the coarse-grained contourite (Facies 2 and 3) and the lowest values in the fine-grained contourites (Facies 1). This fact indicates that strong bottom current activity is linked to winds periods coincident with arid conditions, corresponding to cold phases such as the stadials HE 2 and YD represented by the highest Zr/Al, Si/Si+Al and $mean_{ss}$ values. Weak bottom current activity is related to periods of low winds, during humid conditions, coincident with cold/warm phases in the D/O cycles, represented by low Zr/Al, Si/Si+Al and $mean_{ss}$ values.

CONCLUSIONS

This research illustrates a prime example of how bottom currents affect the construction of contourite drifts, and how fine-grained, mainly muddy contourites can be used in sedimentological and paleoceanographic studies. This work provides new insights into the variability of palaeohydrodynamic changes in bottom currents over the last 24 ka in the SW Mediterranean Sea.

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